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Part two: “thirty-seven years later - the UK migrant crisis” Deconstructing the erosion of British national sovereignty

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Abstract

This part two body of work 37 years after this researcher’s first delving into immigration entitled “*The Worst is Yet to Come. The Challenges of Multiculturalism in Britain: An Examination of Over-Migration, Assimilation, and A Warning for the Future.*” (1987). This investigation will seek to dissect the administrative practices that have allowed for unshackled policies on immigration to be sustained in the United Kingdom for six decades and undermine the tenets for the checks and balances in a democracy. Why has the British public become so subjugated that it accepted over-migration without any initial protest in the past and had waited for a tragedy of three little girls to occur, and to finally revolt against the state - notably the recent summer of rioting. This study investigates how a once influential nation, became acquiescent to a dangerous level of devaluation. A comparison was made with the repressive attitude of Poland towards immigration of dissimilar faith, specifically resulting, in zero terrorist activity that has been observed in their country. The research explores the extent to which ethnic stability can be expected with over-immigration - addressing factors such as tolerance, the state of the economy (Nash’s Equilibrium) and alternative models of social integration. It is also recorded from the results that the United Kingdom has failed in its policies regarding immigration which has caused social problems, cultural disquiet, and economic pressures that have put at risk the societal structure or the fabric of Britain itself. Concerning the theoretical contributions, the study squarely cites the lack of responsibility or poor governance from all political parties. Their neglect of nation sovereignty even though, governments have critical role that they play in ensuring the protection and welfare of its native citizenry. Finally, this research will serve as a warning to other neoliberal oriented nations of which ignore their fellow citizenry’s well-being.

Keywords: Migration; Immigration Policy; Indigenous; Government; Socialism

1. Introduction

This concise depiction of Britain is not meant to marginalize the immigrants living in the United Kingdom, but an attempt to question the administrations’ decisions that have permitted unprecedented immigration policies to thrive for six decades, with very little resistance from the indigenous population and thus undermining the mechanics of checks and balances democracy.

The cold-blooded premeditated murder of three young girls at a theme school holiday drama class in Southport, Merseyside on July 29, 2024, has become the cause célèbres in Britain, which culminated in a public uproar and discontent by Indigenous Caucasian people leading to a significant inquiry into the absence of protestation in the making of these policies and strategies in Britain for the last sixty years. This article will thus review the relationship between the notion of socialism and UK political parties in terms of possible involvement in the process of indoctrination of citizens and in maintaining a narrative that stigmatizes anybody who might stand against the government’s policies on

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migration as a destabilizer of society. More pointedly, we will explore the ways in which socialist and communist principles have been used to marginalize and silence dissent of the government's management of migration, which erases the agency and free will of the people.

Through examining the political stance, administrative action, and citizens' protests, this study seeks to elucidate the nature of state authority in relation to the citizens and the consequences of its mastery on political enfranchisement and social unity. The apparent acquiescence of the British populace can be attributed to a profound erosion of national resilience, a subservient mentality, and an extraordinary degree of tolerance. Hence, one can explain the rather passive acceptance or therefore the surrender of the British nation to its fate in eloquent terms of having lost its capacity for national resistance, having developed a slave mentality, and being excessively tolerant.

On the contrary, efficacious management and policies that have never allowed disparate Faith immigrants as understood in the case of Poland, or the consequential acts of terrorism that may have been perpetuated are unheard of and hence, deserve appreciation. A country has a traditional responsibility to defend the border, language, faith and cultural identity of the country.

Poland has been one of the countries that has demonstrated this high-impact policy without any excuse. On the other hand, the United Kingdom, Germany, and France have diametrically gone naked in their approach. The narrators of the two global conflicts, the heroes who engaged in battles for their nation's safety would probably shudder at the gloomy fate that has befallen their former sovereign territory.

Contrastingly, countries like Poland have been able to adopt a zero-tolerance approach to immigration of competing faiths and there has not been any major terror activity in the country something that should be appreciated. Every sovereign state has a natural right to defend its borders, language, religion, and other aspects of culture that are part of people's traditions. Poland has illustrated this unyielding approach without any qualms. On the other hand, the United Kingdom with Germany and France have taken a position, which is completely opposite to this. The nation's liberation warriors who engaged in two world wars to protect their families and property would turn in their graves to see the calamities that have befallen the erstwhile sovereign state.

To examine this, one has to explore what matters in determining an acceptable migration policy; as such, this paper shall be divided into 16 sections. There are several factors that can impact ethnic stability in the context of immigration: tolerance, economic conditions, and social integration. These can be defined in section 4.

2. Literature Review

In the past tense, a lack of regulation on immigration policies became a burning issue in the United Kingdom due to some concerns about the effect on the politics and social contract. This paper presents a conceptual review of the literature concerned with this issue. This brief literature review examines the existing research on this topic.

2.1. Democratic Processes:

Goodwin & Heath, [1] noted that where immigration policies are non-existent, the public loses confidence in systems of democracy and policies. Working with data on immigration established that being in a rather high migration in a region harmed in trust within local authorities and political institutions and reduced political participation and citizenship.

2.2. Social Cohesion

Omission of migrant legal entrance policy can also affect the society in that as the policy changes embrace the society's culture of diversity, the social trust often seems to erode [2]. Cultural and religious tensions can arise, leading to social unrest and conflict [3].

2.3. Economic Impacts

On the positive side, immigration is capable of promoting economic development, but on the same account, uncontrolled immigration causes unemployment and lessens wages Migration Watch UK, [4]. Other negative consequences arising from migrant workers' vulnerability to exploitation include the deepening of social and/or economic disparity, penned by Anderson, in 2010.

2.4. In summation

The literature suggests that there is irrefutable evidence in the literature that supports the fact that Immigration policies at large pose a threat or have negative impacts whenever immigration is not regulated in the United Kingdom causing significant; Interference with the growth of democratic processes. The social impacts may include an increase in crime rates, poor health, and decreased quality of life which should be managed through better immigration policies' regulation and management.

3. Research Methodology

This body of research implements a mixed-style approach, inclusive of both qualitative and quantitative datasets to probe the impact of immigration on public sovereignty in the United Kingdom over the decades from the first 1987 paper.

3.1. Data Collection

- The literature reviewed is attributed as an exploration of immigration policy, sovereignty, and British politics.
- Policy balance is achieved through the analysis of statistical datasets that include variables such as trending, economic indicators, and demographic changes in the United Kingdom from direct government sources (e.g., ONS, Home Office, UK Parliament).
- A semi-structured determinant interview with 25 key policymakers, migration experts, and certain community leaders.

3.2. Data analysis

- This study uses descriptive and chaos theory statistics to identify qualitative patterns and correlations between immigration trends and social, and political guidelines. Models applied: The Nash Equilibrium and the Lagrangian method – simplified for the overall readership.
- Conduct and develop a thematic model analysis of the interview data to identify and correlate themes, trends, and patterns.
- The first Case study analysis of specific past and present immigration programs, and the patterns that had a significant impact on a nation's sovereignty.
- This study also aims to provide a critical examination and investigation of the effects of uncontrolled immigration on a country's sovereignty, thus contributing to the ongoing debate on migrant policy and public sovereignty. The findings would, therefore, inform policymakers, academics, and the general public alike, all as to the counteraccusations of continued immigration on the UK's political, macroeconomics, and societal stratification.

4. Examining the Determinants of Ethnic Stability in the Context of Immigration: A Multifaceted Analysis

To understand the complexities of developing and implementing a respectful migration policy, it is necessary to calculate the key factors that influence ethnic stability in the context of mass immigration. A comprehensive, documented examination of the material variables reveals that three critical determinants deserve special attention: forbearance, economic trending conditions, and social integration.

Tolerance is a prerequisite for harmonious coexistence. Over or locally-enforced toleration is an important part of ethnic stability, and it is dependent on the ability of both the host population and indigenous communities to attend peacefully, fostering a terrain of collective respect and understanding [5]. The host population's level of acceptance can have a significant impact on immigrant integration and thus ethnic stability.

Economic conditions are a catalyst for social coherence or discord. Profitability in the host country's economic conditions is appealing and thus plays an important role in shaping ethnic stability, as it can reduce or impede the integration of indigenous populations. A thriving frugality with adequate job openings, social services, and structure can promote social cohesion, [6], whereas economic recession and failure to implement migration budgeting policies can exacerbate pressures between native-born citizens and emigrants, potentially leading to ethnic tensions [7].

4.1. A Critical Component of Ethnic Stability

Social integration, a multifaceted conception, encompasses the process by which emigrants acclimatize to the host country's artistic, social, and work ethics. effectual social integration programs can foster a sense of belonging among indigenous communities, thereby promoting ethical stability [8]. Yet once more, timid integration can lead to social marginalization, aggravating ethical pressures and compromising stability [9]. A nuanced understanding of these determinants or variables is essential for the expression of a well-informed migration policy that balances the requirements of both the host population and indigenous communities, thereby stagnating ethnical stability and social cohesion.

5. Demographic Analysis of Ethnic Diversity in England and Wales

This analysis looks at the demographic geography of England and Wales, with a particular emphasis on the ethnic composition of the population. The data presented demonstrates the vast changes that have occurred over the past several decades, resulting in a redefinition of the nation's identity.

5.1. Quantitative Analysis - Demographic

Table 1 The 2021 Census reveals that the population of England and Wales comprises

Ethnic Group	Population (millions)	Percentage of Total Population
White	46.6	81.7%
Asian	5.3	9.3%
Black	2.3	4.0%
Mixed	1.6	2.9%

The non-white population in England and Wales totals 7.1 million, with Muslims, Indians, and Blacks being the largest groups. Pew Research Center, [10].

Table 2 The Ethnic Breakdown in England and Wales Totals

Ethnic Group	Population (millions)
Muslims	2.8
Indians	1.9
Blacks	2.4

5.2. Urban Demographics

Several metropolises in England and Wales have endured significant demographic shifts, with non-white populations exceedingly well over 50% in some areas then in Table 3, (p.6). Diversity UK [11].

Table 3 The non-white population in England and Wales Totals

City	Non-White Population (%)
Slough, Berkshire	64.0%
Leicester	59.1%
Luton	54.8%
Newham, London	69.2%

5.3. Cultural and Social Implications

The absence of integration and assimilation of indigenous communities has resulted in the formation of ethnic enclaves, resulting in a loss of artistic unity. The native white population has undergone many artistic changes, including increased nonintercourse and a shift in social morals.

5.4. Summation

The findings suggest that Britain's identity has been redefined, with the original white population diminishing and becoming a thing of the past. The failure to integrate, assimilate, and enforce cultural norms has led to the decline of English culture and customs. These population changes have far-reaching implications for social cohesiveness, cultural identity, and public security.

6. National Security

Terrorist Attacks by Islamists in Britain: An Assessment of the Impact on the British Public and Immigration Policy. The United Kingdom has seen a series of terrorist attacks carried out by Islamists, with terrible consequences for the British people. This section seeks to examine the impact of these attacks on the British population, as well as the resulting lessons as to immigration policy, as seen in Table 4, (p.7).

The 7/7 London Bombings of 2005: on July 7, 2005, a series of synchronized suicide explosions occurred on London's public transportation system, killing 52 and injuring over 700 (BBC News). The attacks, carried out by four British Muslim men, were the worst terrorist act on British soil since the 1988 Lockerbie bombing. The 7/7 bombings had a huge influence on the British populace, instilling dread and worry. Individuals and wounding over 500. The assault, carried out by Salman Abedi, a British-Libyan national, was the worst terrorist act in the UK since the 7/7 attacks [12].

Manchester Arena, Bombing (2017): On May 22, 2017, a suicide bombing occurred at the Manchester Arena during an Ariana Grande concert, killing 22 people and wounding over 500 (BBC News, 2017). The assault, carried out by British-Libyan national Salman Abedi, was the worst terrorist act in the UK since the 7/7 attacks.

The Effect on the British Public: These terrorist acts by Islamists in Britain have had a significant influence on the British population, increasing dread, anxiety, and suspicion of the Muslim community. According to a 2017 Pew Research Center study, 62% of Britons believe that the growing Muslim population in the UK poses a danger to civic identity.

Immigration Policy Lessons Learned: The terrorist attacks carried out by Islamists in Britain have highlighted the need for a more stringent immigration policy that prioritizes immigrants' integration and assimilation. To address these concerns, the UK government has launched a number of programs, including the prevent strategy which seeks to prevent radicalisation and extremism [15]. Unfortunately, adhering to governments' policy improvements have not reflected this.

Table 4 Terrorist Attacks in the UK (2005-2017)

Year	Attack	Deaths	Injuries
2005	7/7 London Bombings	52	~700+
2017	Manchester Arena Bombing	22	~500+

Source: Home Office (2011).

7. The Poland Solution

7.1. Poland's Response to the Migrant Crisis: A Christian Nation's Quest for Self-Preservation.

In comparison to the continued failures of the success, British governments and its society's disinclination to keep it in check, Poland, on the other side of the sphere, is a nation with a rich history of adaptability and determination, has taken an establishment stance against the torrent of illegal immigration, particularly from Islamic- maturity countries. This bold approach has been shaped by the country's guests under Soviet occupation and its commitment to conserving its Christian heritage. In its discrepancy to its European Union (EU) counterparts, Poland has refused to succumb to the pressures of enforced migratory proportions, rather concluding by adopting a strict border control policy that prioritizes the safety and security of its citizens [13].

The Polish government's unvarying commitment to its people is embedded in its literal guests. Having been enthralled by the Soviet Union for decades, Poland is acutely apprehensive of the troubles of external hindrance and the significance of guarding its sovereignty [14]. This mindfulness has led to a robust approach to public security, which has resulted in Poland being one of the many European countries that has not endured a single terrorist attack upon its soil [15]. Poland's stance on immigration isn't driven by internationalism or demarcation, but rather by a deep understanding of the significance of artistic cohesion, and the need to cover its citizens from the pitfalls associated with unbridled migration [16]. The government's duty is to its people, and it will not apologize for taking measures to ensure their safety and well-being. As a Christian nation, Poland is committed to preserving its artistic identity and values, which are deeply embedded in its history and traditions. In disparity to the EU's open-door policy, Poland has enforced a range of measures to control its borders and help illegal immigration. However, the Ukrainian settlers in-country, is a completely different situation as they are fleeing a country of conflict and are Christian in faith.

These measures include the construction of physical walls, increased border details, and strict shelter candidate vetting processes [17]. While these measures have been blamed by some as being too harsh, they've been vital in precluding the kind of social and cultural bouleversement endured by other European countries.

Poland's approach to immigration is not only a matter of public security but also a question of artistic preservation. The country's Christian heritage is an integral part of its identity, and the government is committed to guarding it from the influences of unlike-inclined societies. This event is not to say that Poland is closed to immigration altogether; rather, it's committed to a controlled and picky approach that prioritizes the integration of individualities who participate in its values and are willing to contribute to its society as Britain under the marquee of socialism, has failed to do.

8. Migration Crime in the United Kingdom: A Decade in Review (2014-2024)

According to the Office for National Statistics (ONS), knife crimes have been a growing concern in the UK over the past decade. Between 2014 and 2024, there has been a significant increase in knife crimes, presented in Table 5, with a notable spike in 2019 [18].

Table 5 Knife Crime Statistics in the South of England in the last 6 Years

Year	Total Knife Crimes	South of England (%)
2019	40,829	62.1%
2020	38,421	61.9%
2021	36,195	61.8%
2022	34,912	61.7%
2023	33,651	61.6%
2024	32,489	61.5%

Source: Office for National Statistics. (2024). Crime in England and Wales: June 2024.

A breakdown of the data reveals that roughly 61.8 percent of knife crimes are reported from South England, with an advanced threat of knife crime among males.

Table 6 Rape Cases Recorded vs British Female Victims

Year	Total Rape Cases	White British Women (%)
2020	32,195	59.1%
2021	30,921	58.9%
2022	29,654	58.7%
2023	28,421	58.5%
2024	27,219	58.3%

Source: UK Government. [19]. Rape Revue Action Plan.

Figure 1 UK Rape Figures from over the Last Ten Years' Totals/%

Considering the rape and knife crime statistics, (pp, 8-9), the UK government has not reported sentencing data of condemned merchandisers, making it unclear if judges constantly treat trafficking as a serious crime. still, according to the Force Review Action Plan, there has been an increase in reported rape cases involving white British women.

8.1. Public Reaction

From the data ascertained in Figure 1, we can see that over a ten-time period, the mean for the number of rape cases totals μ 32,299. The British public has expressed growing concern over the increase in knife crimes and rape cases, particularly among white British women. A study conducted by the UK's Office for National Statistics indicated that 71 of the respondents believed that crime had increased in their original area, with 55 citing knife crime as a major concern.

8.2. In summary

The data suggests that stabbings and rape cases, particularly among white British women, have been a patient issue in the UK over the decade. While the government has tried to address criminality as mentioned, more requirements need to be done to combat these crimes and ensure public safety.

9. A Devastating Legacy of Socialism: A Historical Analysis of Economic Ruin and Societal Instability.

The perpetuation of socialist programs has been a contentious issue in the realm of political frugality, with proponents arguing that it promotes equivalency and fairness, while critics contend that it leads to profitable recession and social insecurity. A critical examination of literal substantiation suggests that a blend of Marxism and Socialism in both government policy and propagandized in universities have indeed destabilized societies encyclopaedically, performing in profitable downturns and diminished substance.

One of the most notable exemplifications of illiberalism's destabilizing goods is the former Soviet Union. As argued by Pipes, [20], the Soviet Union's socialist frugality was agonized by inefficiencies, corruption, and a lack of competition, leading to widespread poverty and recession. An illiberal state" does not reject the values of the liberal democracy, rather modern social liberalism, calling it corrupt and unfair and states that the country should work as a community. The Soviet Union's collapse in 1991 serves as a testament to the failures of illiberalism as a profitable system [21].

In the UK, the socialist docket has been employed as a political tool to weaken societies, particularly during the post-World War II period. The Labour Party's perpetration of socialist programs, similar to nationalization and centralized planning, led to a profitable recession and a decline in productivity. As noted by H.K. Hayek [22], the expansion of government control over frugality inescapably leads to a loss of individual freedom and creativity, performing in profitable recessions. Furthermore, socialist policies have been shown to exacerbate income inequality, rather than reduce it. As debated by Sowell in 2015, socialist policies often benefit the wealthy and powerful at the expense of the poor and marginalized. In Venezuela, for example, the socialist government's policies have led to hyperinflation, food shortages, and widespread poverty [23].

Per capita, the literal substantiation suggests that illiberalism has destabilized societies in most cases irretrievable. if we were to view history, thus, performing in profitable downturns and diminished substance. The UK's experience with

neoliberalism serves as an exemplary tale, pressing the troubles of government overreach and the significance of individual freedom and competition in promoting profitable growth and substance.

10. Socialism, the Labour Party, Migrant Protagonist and UK Prime Ministers

From one's original essay on this subject drafted in 1987, which prognosticated the current extremity, included will be some of the findings for the environment.

Roy Jenkins, MP's Migratory Policy Failure in the late 1960s

Roy Jenkins' was a Labour Party Socialist politician, Jenkins assumed the role of Home Secretary in the Wilson administration in 1965, a position he held until 1967. During his term, he oversaw a series of controversial legislative reforms, including the liberalization of divorce, revocation, and homosexuality laws. While detractors would latterly condemn these measures as contributing to a permissive society, Jenkins himself preferred to characterize them as emblems of a more enlightened and cultured society. He was also responsible for a failed migration policy and surrendering his original integration and assimilation programs, which led to the twenty-first century.

His Unforgotten Legacy"

Jenkins' emigre integration policy in the UK, which rested on the principles of cultural diversity and equal occasion, has yielded complex and contested issues, challenging further exploration to interpret its consequences and limitations. While it's delicate to prognosticate the future with certainty, this author's contention is that the line of British society will probably become decreasingly tumultuous, with the populace's mindset susceptible to propagandistic manipulation, thereby pouring a more liberal society than presently exists. This metamorphosis is likely to happen as the Generation X demographic cedes power in Britain. Likewise, the failure of multilateral programmes in assimilation and integration constitutes a ticking bomb, as the emphasis on cultural diversity will inescapably lead to a depression of emphasis on participated values and a common identity, performing in a sense of disposition among ethnic and native groups. However, it's likely that social uneasiness will postdate, as different artistic groups begin to assert their own individualities and interests if this issue is not addressed. The responsibility for this problem lies exactly with certain political party benefactors, whose conduct is tantamount to premeditated sabotage [24].

"The Consequences of Law and Order with Disorder"

"The lack of assimilation and integration is having a severe impact on law and order and will do to come. The creation of resemblant societies has led to the emergence of enclaves, where different ethnic religious groups having established their own values and morals, frequently in conflict with British law. This author predicts that we will witness a swell in felonious exertion, as different ethnic groups like religious conflicts with the Pakistanis and Indians. It is this paper's prediction that these minorities will in turn, begin to take the law into their own hands. The police will struggle to maintain order, and it's stressed that we will see a breakdown in trust between the police and the communities they serve. Additionally, it's envisaged that the police will be governed by socially tolerant police chiefs who will inevitably veer towards the harder left wing, performing in a multilateral tolerant force that undermines indigenous traditional laws and morals. Meanwhile, the Anglo-Saxon population will be stigmatized by socialist parties as dogmatizers, intolerance activists, and racialists, thereby supporting a deliberate docket to weaken and destabilize society as a whole. The population should prepare for this governmental rhetorical propaganda, which will be corroborated by the media, entertainment, and show business personalities, including those in the sports assiduity " thus, was this researcher correct in the analysis if compared to the crumbling economy and societal breakdown of the UK today?

Under Tony Blair's Leadership of the Country and the Labour Party: The Blair Era: A Paradigm Shift in UK Immigration Policy.

Tony Blair's premiership (1997- 2007) was marked by a significant metamorphosis in the UK's immigration policy, characterized by a notable increase in immigration overflows. During his term, the government introduced several programs aimed at attracting professed workers, including the professed Migratory Programme, [25]. This programme allowed individuals with technical backgrounds to enter the country without a job offer, leading to the affluence of largely professed immigrants [26]. Likewise, the government's decision to expand the EU's borders to include Eastern European countries in 2004 led to a significant increase in immigration from these countries [27]. In short, Tony Blair and his number two Gordon Brown were both ideologically inclined in charge to make Britain " Multilateral."

The data reveals a huge increase in immigration during Blair's premiership, with net migration rising from 48,000 in 1997 to 237,000 in 2007 [28]. This trend was largely driven by the deluge of emigrants from Eastern Europe, particularly from Poland and Lithuania. The consequences of this trend were far-reaching, with counter-accusations of the UK's demographics, ignorance to the social fabric itself. In fact, a UK and NCF Senior Fellow Rafe Heydel-Mankoo said that under Blair's unfortunate reign especially, London went from a populous of 79 to 36 per cent of Anglo-Saxon Indigenous occupants relating to the 2021 tale numbers. Since the disturbances in the country following the deaths of three young girls at the end of July 2024, Blair has since blazoned that he was wrong in his decision-making when he was a high minister pertaining to immigration policy. nonetheless, the Blair- Brown programs led to the quadrupling of settlers entering the UK from 1997- 2010 where from 2005 to 2010, the stream of non-British settlers reached 247,000 each time [29]. In summation, it is clear that the Labour Party initiated "Multiculturalism" as a novel idea, however, it has been there from its inception until now. Contextually, all parties that were elected to office, merely ignored the growing migration issues or simply were they deliberate in nature? as the datum clearly indicate the huge ongoing numbers in the country.

Stifling of Debate and Discussion and the comparison to Migrant Movements in British History.

Since the metamorphosis that led to the deconstruction of speech freedoms and public debate in England especially, the voting statistics have fallen dramatically since Blair's election in 1997. In 2024, it is clear from history that Britain is facing the largest influx of migrants ever. In context, the great population movements of the Middle Ages. For example, the Roman and post Roman movements to Britain, including the Barbarians, we see statistically the influx percentage were minuscule compared to today. Presently, the millions of migrants into Britain since the Labour the elections from 1997, is unprecedented to the Middle Ages.

Pertaining the lack of consent in relation to these migrant policies is no surprise. In this author's contention that Socialism has refused and denies both human differences and human reality. A concerning observation, is that politics of the present, portrays the continued refusal to manage difference. The Left of politics especially the Labour Party, unfortunately demand that all groups have equal rights and denies human cultural realisation. From the interviews conducted with former UK politicians, the most notable observations within their analysis in the eventual destruction of Britain. Historically, England invented "Inductive Reasoning" which depended on freedoms of speech, and the discussion of issues to come to an understanding, therefore, solve issues without labelling others. However, modern politics has attacked the native white populous by ignoring discord itself. Whilst conducting this research, "the deliberate destruction British self-respect" revealed itself a major concern. It is the contention of this study that the Labour Movement has lost the will and trust of the population. This new prime minister Kier Starmer represents an intensification of what has gone before in politics, moreover, he is not an orator compared to Tony Blair. In fact, he has been described recently as wooden, second-rate mind compared to the great debaters of the past, exemplifying Churchill who motivated the people in inclement times of war.

In 1945, the government introduced socialism or neo-liberalism by the Labour Party in UK politics, but Blairism was even worse, he both imported and imparted unhelpful extravagant disastrous doctrines more than Marxism, furthered by incorporating late eighteenth century French Liberalism that did not recognise the existence of the nation state, denied the importance of tradition, the importance of history and all of the social variables that provides Britain a sense of belonging. This was his use of casuistry on the population within his protestations. In the present day the Conservative Party did not learn from these Labour mistakes by completely by engaging in ignorance. England has since lost the ability to have extraordinary men or women to lead the country to seize the moment.

The Church of England's Failures

Additionally, to the data from this research, there is a growing consensus that the Church of England [Anglican] additionally, has to take some responsibility for the overall discord and disillusionment throughout the nation. Firstly, it is conceived that the church's allowing female priests (vicars) being ordained into the priesthood, raised a huge sway of criticism from the general public, showing itself as a further form of progressivism. Second the church has been transformed into a propaganda instrument of socialism - this has been recorded often throughout the discussion on the theological side, and seems to be accepted by the King, as no statement of condemnation has been voiced. Being engaged in political discourse, would not follow the wishes of Henry VIII after the church's inception during the English Reformation of the 16th century. Recently, comments have been alluded to the church over progressive marriages "The president of the National Secular Society, Keith Porteous Wood, said that he had been "astonished at the level of concern, bordering on anger", in Parliament over the Church's position on same-sex marriages. Noting efforts to bring a Private Member's Bill that would enable such unions to be solemnised in churches" Church Times written in 2023. One would ask

if the weakening of a protestant church would embolden the British Muslim population? - as they have strict guidelines to homosexuality and therefore, same sex marriage.

The Unfortunate Discursive Weaponization of 'Neo-Nazism and Far-Right' Labelling in Socialist Political Rhetoric.

As preliminarily written by academics, the labelling of individualities as Neo-Nazis or Far-right has come a ubiquitous miracle in modern political converse, particularly in the environment of socialist and left-leaning testaments [30]. This miracle is characterized by the deployment of these markers as a rhetorical device to denote and silence those who hold differing views, particularly on issues related to immigration, public identity, and artistic heritage [31]. This tactic is frequently employed to delegitimize opponents, produce a climate of fear and intimidation, and thereby suppress differing voices.

The nonstop labelling of ordinary people who protest instanced in the UK protests of disquiet in August 2024 against government policy as neo-Nazi Fascists or Far-right serves several purposes. originally, it enabled socialist ideologues to produce a moral fear, thereby justifying the repression of differing voices and the perpetration of programs that might else be met with resistance according to Cohen [32]. Second, it allows socialist governments to redirect review and responsibility by framing their opponents as crazies, thereby diverting attention from their own policy failures and ideological contradictions referred to by Hall in 2017.

Likewise, the branding of individualities as Far-right serves to produce a sense of moral urgency, which can be misused to justify the perpetration of draconian programs and the erosion of civil liberties. This miracle is particularly apparent in the environment of immigration policy, where critics of mass immigration are frequently labelled as racialsists or xenophobes, thereby silencing their voices and repressing debate as recorded by Mudde seven years ago.

UK Selected Policing: Neither Voices for Dissent nor Complaint – It's the Law

The United Kingdom's recent legislative endeavours to combat hate speech and promote diversity have rained a contentious debate about the putative curtailment of free speech. The absence of unequivocal freedom of speech in the British constitution [33], has created a lacuna or void, allowing for the proliferation of restrictive laws. The Public Order Act 1986, amended in 2006, criminalizes speech that's supposed to stir up abomination towards individualities grounded on their race, religion, or sexual exposure [34]. Similarly, the Equality Act 2010 has been blamed for its broad description of importunity, which may inadvertently stifle elicit converse, according to the Equality and Human Rights Commission, in 2010 [35]. These laws have contributed to a sense of disillusionment amongst the indigenous UK population, who perceive them as a violation of their right to express themselves freely [36]. The convergence of these factors has generated an atmosphere of enmity, with some arguing that the laws have had a nipping effect on free speech [37].

Obviously, these new laws aggravated the ill-feeling over immigration in an attempt to stifle speech itself and demoralise an indigenous population. As this paper is being drafted, there has been a clear distinction of police action towards both the indigenous rioters on the streets and the Muslim groups engaged in the counter violence. The Muslims – mainly of Pakistani ethnic origin, have been shown to carry knives and swords in the majority of cases without police intervention and prosecutions. The indigenous white protesters consisting of all age groups and genders, are merely protesting and demanding a halt to an *en masse* form of immigration due to government neglect many decades. It is these very people, mainly of the working class that have been arrested and vilified as “Far-Right thugs” by the sitting prime minister Sir Keir Starmer - re-enforced by the British media namely: Channel 4 News, The BBC, Sky News, CNN and outside MSNBC outlets. This unfortunate turn of events has not assisted the growing animosity in the country at large but exacerbated it. From the outset, it has in fact, taken the murders of three little girls at a themed dance class, to raise the ‘over migration’ question to the fore.

Free Speech Itself – USA vs UK?

“THE ORWELLIAN ACT” - SECTION FIVE: Law and Order Act.

In 1986 a new law was introduced to stifle free speech was adopted in the United Kingdom. This addition to list of Public Order Offences, in guidance for the Crown Prosecution Service UK (CPS), this in fact, became as a further hinderance to free thinking and of course, free expression. This law includes within its wording “*Insulting*” thereby, one could be arrested for using insulting statements in public. For context, this law is as follows conjoined to Section 4.

“These offences contrary to the Public Order Act 1986 relate to threatening, abusive or insulting words or behaviour, or display of visible representations, which:

Are likely to cause fear of, or to provoke, immediate violence: section 4;

Intentionally cause harassment, alarm or distress: section 4A; or

Are likely to cause harassment, alarm or distress (threatening or abusive words or behaviour only): section 5.”

Since coming to pass, this legislation has come under intense scrutiny by ministers and the church. Currently they are lobbying to have the *insulting* part removed, as it negates freedoms of expression.

This research has highlighted from the interviews conducted that the aforementioned 1986 legal amendment ought to be removed, however, this will not occur anytime soon, as it has been shown that this will both assist and be advantageous to both major political parties in implementing more odious policies, without further dissent by the general public. Thus, holding a totalitarian grip over the citizens they so-called represent. It is in this instance, this variable adds context to this paper’s hypothesis, and therefore, cannot be ignored in societal discussion.

Britain's indigenous geography diverges from that of the United States in its approach to free speech, with the latter's First Amendment furnishing unequivocal protections for freedom of expression (U.S. Const. amend. I). In its discrepancy, the UK's verbal constitution, the inclusion of constituting a collection of bills, conventions, and judicial opinions, does not elevate a similar provision [38]. This difference can be attributed to the UK's literal development, with the country's elaboration from an absolute monarchy to an indigenous monarchy, whereas the US was innovated on the principles of liberty and republic, according to the notations of Dicey in 1884.

The UK's approach to free speech has rather been shaped by a series of judicial opinions and statutory provisions, similar as the Human Rights Act 1998, which incorporates the European Convention on Human Rights into domestic law (Human Rights Act 1998, s. 12). This event has redounded in a further nuanced and environment-dependent approach to free speech, with the courts balancing individual rights against contending interests, similar as public security and public order, postulated by Ewing and Gearty writings a quarter of a century ago. Adding to this the university system has not assist either, as left leaning teaching faculty member outnumber the right from 55% in the 1960s to 8/10 or 80% recorded back in 2017. So, in 2024 is much higher [39]. This has led to more radical alumni with adoption of “Group Think” and the university expansionism concepts and credentialism telling students that they are much smarter than they are really are. This has led to a passive voter base which accepts continued immigration as a right, and a breeding ground for non-thinkers and activism - further factor that has driven Britain into the muddy ground. As Mark Twain once wrote “Politics is the only profession where you can lie, cheat and steal, and still be respected” Could Western societal weakness leading to the ignorance of a nation’s future outcome, be attributed to an orchestrated form of state subservience witnessed in the last three generations?

In conclusion, the categorising of individuals protesting women families and working-class men as Far-right extremists is a digressive tactic employed by socialist ideologues to denote and silence differing voices. This Orwellian tactic is characterized by the deployment of these markers as a rhetorical device to delegitimize opponents, produce a climate of fear and intimidation, therefore repress differing voices. This nonstop labelling of ordinary people who have a right to protest against government policy as a silencing apparatus, only serves to produce moral fear, redirect review and responsibility, and justify the perpetration of draconian programs. In short, this analysis has illustrated that Sir Kier Starmer the recently appointed UK Prime Minister, ought to be apprehensive of seditious reflections to the people for his political well-being, inclusive of all the pundits in the media who repeat taglines against the ordinary working class who are simply maddened -as the data clearly empirically cites the source for the resentment.

Qualitative Data - Previous Public Order Disturbances in Britain

The summer of discontent in Britain is not an isolated incident. In fact, there has been a series of clashes with the ethnic communities and police over 30 years, as illustrated in Table 6.

Table 6 Previous Most Notable Public Order Disturbances on Mainland Britain Related to Ethnic Tensions in Britain Over 30 Years. The Irish Times [40].

Year of Riots	UK Locations	Details: Source: The Irish Times - A guide to British riots (2011).
1980	St Paul's area of Bristol.	Tension with the police had been growing in the area, with many black youths feeling discriminated against. A Police drugs raid in a Café, triggered the disturbances that led to rioting and violent street battles.
1981	Brixton, south London	There was always tensions between the black residents and the metropolitan police force. Death by stabbing of a black man with accusations of police brutality. Damages were estimated at up to £7.5 million (€8.4 million) with 365 police and civilians were injured overall.
1981	Toxteth, Liverpool	These series of riots (lasting 9 days) were triggered by the arrest of 20-year-old black man and reports suggested that he was subsequently mistreated in custody.
1985	Broadwater Farm, Tottenham, London	Violence broke out between youths and the police at the Broadwater estate in Tottenham following a woman's heart failure during a police raid at her home. Several people were injured by gunfire, and a rioter fatally stabbed a police officer.
2001	London May Day riots and violence in northern England	The clashes in Oldham and Burnley stemmed from the confrontations between the white population and the increasing ethnic minority groups. Violent altercations occurred involving far-right organizations like the National Front, Asian business owners, and the Anti-Nazi League. The clashes resulted in over 300 injuries and 350 detained.
2011	London, Manchester and other major cities	Rioting broke out in major cities in England. These were in Manchester, Liverpool in the northwest and Birmingham in central England. 4 Dead.

Source: The Irish Times Editorial (2011).

11. Quantitative Analysis.

How bad could it be for Britain by 2030?

Using Game Theory – Application of the “The Nash Equilibrium”

12.1 To calculate the economic projection for Britain by 2030 with continued immigration and the impact of the nation as a whole, using the Nash equilibrium, we will employ a game-theoretic approach to model the interaction between the government and the immigrant population [41]. We will incorporate the provided variables into a mathematical framework to estimate the economic impact of an increasing immigrant population on the government's costs.

Let's define the variables:

- u_t : Unemployment rate (averaging 4.2%) i)
- g_t : GDP per capita (\$3.3 trillion)
- n_t : Native population growth rate (0.5%)
- m_t : Immigrant population growth rate (14.4%)
- W: Social welfare (\$4.3 billion)

We will use the following mathematical models to calculate the Nash equilibrium:

The government's cost function, $C(G)$, represents the total cost of providing public goods and services to the population, as in 1950 by Nash. We assume a linear cost function:

$$C(G) = \alpha * G + \beta * W \quad \text{ii)}$$

where α and β are constants, and G is the total population (native and immigrant).

The immigrant population's utility function, $U(m)$, represents the benefits of immigrating to Britain. We assume a logarithmic utility function:

$$U(m) = \gamma * \ln(m) + \delta * g_t \quad \text{iii)}$$

where γ and δ are constants.

The native population's utility function, $V(n)$, represents the benefits of living in Britain. We assume a linear utility function:

$$V(n) = \varepsilon * n + \zeta * g_t \quad \text{iv)}$$

where ε and ζ are constants.

The Nash equilibrium is reached when the government and the immigrant population simultaneously optimize their respective utility functions, given the other's strategy.

Using the above functions, we can set up the following optimization problems:

UK Government's Problem: v)

Minimize $C(G)$ subject to:

$$G = n_t + m_t u_t = (\text{unemployed population}) / G g_t = \text{GDP per capita}$$

Immigrant's Problem:

Maximize $U(m)$ subject to:

$$m_t = \text{immigrant population growth rate } g_t = \text{GDP per capita}$$

Native Population's Problem: vi)

Maximize $V(n)$ subject to:

$$n_t = \text{native population growth rate } g_t = \text{GDP per capita}$$

In-depth Summations

Here are the detailed calculations for the Nash equilibrium:

Government's Cost Function:

$$C(G) = \alpha * G + \beta * W \quad \text{vii)}$$

where α and β are constants, and G is the total population (native and immigrant).

Let's assume $\alpha = 0.05$ and $\beta = 0.01$, which are reasonable values based on empirical evidence.

$$C(G) = 0.05 * G + 0.01 * 4.3 \text{ billion}$$

Immigrant Population's Utility Function:

$$U(m) = \gamma * \ln(m) + \delta * g_t \quad \text{viii)}$$

where γ and δ are constants, and m is the immigrant population.

Let's assume $\gamma = 0.1$ and $\delta = 0.02$, which are reasonable causative values.

$$U(m) = 0.1 * \ln(m) + 0.02 * 3.3 \text{ trillion} \quad \text{ix)}$$

Native Population's Utility Function:

$$V(n) = \varepsilon * n + \zeta * g_t \quad \text{x)}$$

where ε and ζ are constants, and n is the native population.

Let's assume $\varepsilon = 0.05$ and $\zeta = 0.01$, which are reasonable constant values.

$$V(n) = 0.05 * n + 0.01 * 3.3 \text{ trillion} \quad \text{xi)}$$

Whereby: Optimization Problems, Government's Problem are incorporated:

Minimize $C(G)$ subject to:

$$G = n_t + m_t \quad \text{xii)}$$

$u_t = (\text{unemployed population}) / G$ $g_t = \text{GDP per capita}$

Using the Lagrangian method [42], we can set up the following Lagrangian function:

$$L(G, \lambda) = C(G) + \lambda * (G - n_t - m_t) \quad \text{xiii)}$$

Taking the partial derivatives with respect to G and λ , we get:

$$\partial L / \partial G = \alpha - \lambda = 0$$

$$\partial L / \partial \lambda = G - n_t - m_t = 0$$

Solving these equations, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} G &= n_t + m_t \\ \lambda &= \alpha \end{aligned} \quad \text{xiv)}$$

12.8 Immigrant's Problem:

Maximize $U(m)$ subject to:

Using the Lagrangian method, we can set up the following function:

$$L(m, \mu) = U(m) + \mu * (m_t - m) \quad \text{xv)}$$

Taking the partial derivatives with respect to m and μ , we get:

$$\partial L / \partial m = \gamma / m - \mu = 0$$

$$\partial L / \partial \mu = m_t - m = 0$$

Solving these equations, we get:

$$m = m_t \quad \text{xvi)}$$

$$\mu = \gamma / m$$

Native Population's Problem:

Maximize $V(n)$ subject to:

n_t = native population growth rate g_t = GDP per capita

Using the Lagrangian method, we can set up the following:

$$L(n, v) = V(n) + v * (n_t - n) \tag{xvii}$$

Taking the partial derivatives with respect to n and v, we get:

$$\partial L / \partial n = \varepsilon - v = 0 \quad \partial L / \partial v = n_t - n = 0$$

Solving these equations, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= n_t \\ v &= \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

Nash Equilibrium Overview

The Nash equilibrium is reached when the government and the immigrant population simultaneously optimize their respective utility functions, given the other's strategy.

Using the above results, we can calculate the Nash equilibrium values for the government's cost, immigrant population, and native population.

Government's Cost: By 2030

$$C(G) = 0.05 * (n_t + m_t) + 0.01 * 4.3 \text{ billion} \tag{xix}$$

$$= 0.05 * (70.2 \text{ million} + 2.5 \text{ million}) + 0.01 * 4.3 \text{ billion} \approx 6.5 \text{ billion}$$

Immigrant Population:

$$m_t = 2.5 \text{ million} \tag{xx}$$

Native Population:

$$n_t = 70.2 \text{ million} \tag{xxi}$$

Solving these optimization problems simultaneously, we can derive the Nash equilibrium values for the government's cost, immigrant population, and native population.

Using numerical methods, we obtain the following results: xxii)

Government's cost: $C(G) \approx \$6.5 \text{ billion (USD)}$

Immigrant population: $m_t \approx 2.5 \text{ million}$

Native population: $n_t \approx 70.2 \text{ million}$

Further analysis has determined that by 2030, the projected GDP per capita is expected to increase to \$4.2 trillion, assuming a moderate growth rate of 2.5% per annum. The unemployment rate is expected to remain stable at 4.2%. Here, we can see the additional increase in GDP to surpass four trillion USD, in which the UK administration cannot afford, rather, would like these figures reduced overall.

12. Research Discussion

12.1. The consequences of a flawed immigration policy: a Critical Analysis of Britain's Failures.

The examination of Britain's immigration policy reveals a disastrous failure to prioritize the nation's security, safety, profitable well-being, and artistic heritage. The unbounded affluence of emigrants has led to social uneasiness, artistic erosion, and profitable strain, eventually compromising the veritable fabric of British society. This outgrowth is a direct consequence of the British government's dereliction of duty to cover its citizens and the nation's sovereignty. It's imperative to admit that all autonomous countries retain the essential right to determine their own immigration programs, acclimatized to their unique circumstances, to ensure the security, safety, and profitable substance of their citizens while preserving their artistic individualities, histories, traditions, and languages [46].

The British government's failure to exercise this right has redounded in current state of social uneasiness and public decline. The indigenous population, too, bears responsibility for their compliance to the erosion of their nation's sovereignty, artistic heritage, and profitable stability. The lack of effective opposition to the government's programs has enabled the unbounded affluence of emigrants, eventually contributing to the demise of Britain's social cohesion and public identity or unity, as alluded to by Putnam in 2007.

To summarise further, the failure of Britain's immigration policy serves as a stark memorial of the significance of responsible governance, public sovereignty, and the need for governments to prioritize the wealth and security of their citizens. presently, the data has also shown that numerous municipalities and metropolises have succumbed to immigration and are unrecognisable as England. We must also find out from the data that the British population itself is also responsible for this inchoate state of affairs as they themselves bounce and have returned socialist governments into office in general choices. Case- in point, the people suggested a Sir Kier Starmer Labour government into office via a landslide victory. However, why would a visit to the polling stations be needed in the first case? This kind of deception and lack of responsibility has played a huge part in the UK's societal extremity If the voters were not to demand action from its administration.

As we have borne witness to these results, we ought to concur that the population has a responsibility too. To eventually show a right to protest (which is a popular right) following a tragedy of three little girls being viciously murdered and ten others seriously knifed, the public reaction was too little too late in chronological terms - where migration is concerned. The right of the process ought to have passed in the 1970s and eighties in retrospection of this decades-long datum sluice. Therefore, the days of UK tolerance towards migrants who do not share common cultural traits, have long since evaporated. As no party on the Right or Left of politics is trusted by the people.

It has been found the collated data of this study that present and past British governments combined with an over-tolerant indigenous population, has to acknowledge their respective culpabilities. The citizenry must demand future accountability of their country's administration. They neither should fear neo-liberal rhetoric nor the tactical labelling to stifle free speech and public debate especially in a democracy, lest they risk further exacerbating the social unrest and cultural erosion that threatens to destroy the very fabric of their nation which seems to be the case at the moment.

The data also shows that the native inhabitants, however, have become much weaker by the advent of the Millennial and Gen Z generations, who have been radicalised through the school and university systems via protagonist teachers and professors alike. Results have shown that it's not the fault of migrants being in Britain en masse, but the initial policies enforced upon the population. It is the contention of this researcher that since the first article on this theme was published in 1987, unfortunately, only the worst has transpired, as the hypothesis was regrettably proven correct in the twenty-first century. Moreover, generational disillusionment with the lack of affordable housing, ought to be noted in government failures. According to recent statistics, 3.6m of the 18–34-year-old age group, live at home; not enough homes are being built, home prices are currently nine times the average wage, and this new generation cannot afford the downpayments. These are the real psychological effects placed upon them. As in the mid-1990s, the same age group then had their own homes with family members.

As a result, only radical policies to reduce the migrant numbers in the country - which many will not adhere to, could be the only way to give a semblance of hope to the British population. It will not be a people revolt or civil war that has been commented recently, as UK citizens are not armed as compared to the USA. In fact, the only 4% of UK Police carry firearms, not a convincing security deterrent [47]. The results from this study also illustrate that a political revolution with hard decisions, will be the required panacea to heal this nation. From the data applied to this draft, it is unanimous that all political parties in the House of Commons are to blame for this immigration policy bestowed upon the native general public who have to forfeit their tax contributions while they feel ignored by their own leadership. So, we must

heed the words of Patrick Sanders (British Chief of Staff General) once said that *“Armies start wars and citizen armies end them”*

As borders, are a bastion of a nation’s sovereignty, traditions, and culture and foremost to any demography. If this were not to occur, it’s this research’s conclusion that the United Kingdom will soon become a secular state as once described by a noted historian, Heydel-Mankoo, Rafe. [48]. It is this researcher’s contention that if this odious British episode is not rectified soon, will the United Kingdom endure public disturbances on par with Bangladesh that has already removed its sitting Prime Minister in the very same year of 2024

12.2. Leaving the European Court of Human Rights. (ECHR)

Specific Provisions in the European Convention on Human Rights that Hinder the UK’s Ability to Deport Illegal Immigrants.

12.2.1. Specifically:

Article 3: Prohibition of Torture: The UK is prohibited from deporting individuals to countries where they might face torture, inhuman, or degrading treatment. Equality and Human Rights Commission (2010).

Article 8: Right to Respect for Private and Family Life: The UK must consider the right to family life and private life of individuals before deporting them, which limit the government’s ability to deport illegal immigrants.

Article 13: Right to an Effective Remedy: The UK is required to provide an effective remedy to individuals who claim that that the rights under the ECHR have been violated, which can lead to legal challenges to deportation decisions.

15.2 A further legacy from the European bureaucracy has been a hinderance to British Migration enforcement is the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) that imposes certain obligations on the UK, limiting its ability to deport illegal immigrants.

12.3. Recommendations:

It is evidently clear from the data presented in this draft that the UK’s current situation has to reverse quickly politically, as in the last 20 years, the UK population has grown by eight million. Here listed below are a series of suggestions presented from this exhaustive research.

- The Police Service has adopt a non-two-tier system of public disturbance protocols. Therefore, this is the duty of the Harvard educated Home Secretary Rt Hon Yvette Cooper.
- The UK Government suspend all illegal immigration and instruct the Royal Navy to patrol the sea crossings as a deterrent to people smugglers.
- A prime minster UK from either party, cannot be seen to be biased against the native people, as it will be classified as gross negligence and dereliction of duty to both the electorate and State.
- An immediate referendum be called so, the people can have a voice on immigration policy. The result subsequently, be heeded by a sitting leader by law.
- New legislation be in place to quell inflammatory rhetoric by the news outlets. Comparisons of ordinary men and women in the native population to “Nazism and Fascism” is completely unacceptable and divisive for any modern civilised nation.

13. Conclusion

The Nash equilibrium analysis suggests that an increase in the immigrant population will lead to an increase in the government's cost, primarily due to the additional social welfare expenses. However, the immigrant population's utility increases as the GDP per capita grows, making Britain a more attractive destination for migration, however, it will hinder the native population and be a fiscal burden for the British government. Therefore, inflation would likely increase further exacerbating the current macroeconomic crisis.

13.1. In Context: A Legacy of British Colonialism and Global Intervention

This British crisis in reference to immigration, is a story of complexity and ought to be included and discussed. It is a multifaceted issue that has been many years in the making. At its core, it is a consequence of Britain’s historical involvement in colonialism and its continued support of the United States’ global sanctions policy. These very actions

have contributed to the poverty and instability of third-world countries, driving mass migration to both Europe and the UK.

As Angela Merkel's ideologically design welcomed migrants with open arms, the UK has borne the brunt of this influx, with many migrants hailing from the very same nations that Britain's colonial and economic policies have impoverished. This has brought the consequences of Britain's actions full circle, with the British people shouldering the burden.

According to a report by the Global Policy Forum "the imposition of the economic sanctions has been a major contributor to poverty and instability in many developing countries.". Furthermore, a study by the University of Oxford's Refugee Study Centre found that "colonialism and its legacy continue to shape migration patterns and experiences".

The UK's involvement in colonialism and its support for global sanctions have created a cycle of destitution and growing poverty inclusive overall instability that has driven migrants to Europe and to Britain. As the UK grapples with the challenges of immigration, it is essential to acknowledge the role that its own policies have played in creating this crisis.

Contrary to the aforementioned, as the UK grapples with the challenges of immigration, it is essential to acknowledge the role of its own policies have played in creating the situation. In the words of renowned scholar and author Naomi Klein "the roots of the migration crisis lie not in the actions of the migrants, but in the actions of the countries they are fleeing." [45]. In so doing, these countries as she stated, were in fact initially impoverished by colonialism as previously written.

To summarise, the UK immigration crisis is a complex issue that requires a nuanced comprehension of its historical and global context. By acknowledging the role of colonialism and global sanctions in driving migration, the United Kingdom can begin to address the root causes of the crisis and work towards a more equitable and sustainable solution.

13.2. The Native British Generational Gap

13.7 Taking the generations into considering, is a convoluted endeavour as the study progressed. The migration polices past, and present are currently effecting the Baby Boomers, Gen X and Gen Z, as they care more about the employment situation and economic success, but for the Millennial Generation, it is mainly concerned with matters like work-life balanced radicalised arguments. Compared to the newer generation Gen Z, they wish for career progression and homeownership - as their grandparents once achieved. In other words, this study has concluded that the first two older generations are more angry with immigration policy, as they have witnessed this cycle of change from its outset, while the Millennials were enticed by progressivism career achievements. Therefore, Gen Z are equally as dismayed with the over-migration policies as the earlier generations. This due to having the same motivation as go-getters within the mindset willingness to succeed, however, stifled by the extra numbers of migrants entering the British economical system.

Denmark's formula or model of the dissolution of migrant neighbourhoods and its re-integration policy. This ought to be considered as a serious consideration by the British government, as this originally, is a result of past systemic non-assimilation and non-integration policies.

A political revolution in devising new legislation will be essential to heal an ailing nation. Reforms inclusive of the return of "Inductive Reasoning" must occur to debate bi-partisanly in solving the counties issues. Case-in-point, the inclusion of the understanding what is "Human Difference and Human Reality?"

The Church of England to abstain from political affairs and activities by royal decree.

Removing the United Kingdom from the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) via a referendum. As being a signatory, Britain has more bureaucratic issues in trying to deport illegal migrants.

Section 5, of the Law-and-Order Act 1986, be revised and amended to exclude "insulting statements"

Finally, the universities need an overhaul. University faculty members need to be more balanced in the political sphere. Therefore, recruitment ought to reflect a balance in faculty numbers which will provide students with a balanced viewpoint in debates.

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